

Implementation of Inherently Safer Design and OHS Aspects as well as FLARESIM Simulation in Ammonia Plant Design to Ensure Safety for Workers and Surrounding Communities

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Abstract: Every chemical company has a significant risk of accidents, particularly ammonia plants that involve highly flammable and explosive chemicals such as CH₄, H₂, and NH₃. This makes the ammonia industry one of the most hazardous sectors. For instance, a workplace accident in August 2013, which resulted in the deaths of 15 factory workers, occurred at Shanghai Weng's Cold Storage Industrial Co. Ltd in Baoshan, eastern Shanghai. The incident was caused by a liquid ammonia leak from a cryogenic storage refrigeration unit. This event highlights the dangers posed by ammonia plants to both workers and surrounding communities. Therefore, it is crucial to enhance awareness among workers and develop occupational safety knowledge to protect personnel. One effective approach is the implementation of occupational health and safety (OHS) measures and the design of plants that adhere to national and international standards. In this regard, PT Enggang Ammonia is currently developing a plant to increase production, with a liquid ammonia storage capacity of 50,000 tons. The outer boundary of the plant site is approximately 500 meters from residential areas. To ensure the plant operates safely for both workers and nearby residents, the plant design must incorporate safety considerations, particularly by implementing inherently safer design (ISD) principles. The inherently safer design principles include minimize, substitute, moderate, and simplify. Reducing the use of raw materials such as CH₄ and substituting them with alternatives is challenging, as the required raw material quantities are fixed to achieve the designated product output, and CH₄ remains the primary available raw material. Since the technology employed is the well-established Kellogg Brown & Root (KBR) process, simplifying the process is not considered to prevent a decline in process reliability. The moderate principle is applied by establishing hazardous area classifications for key equipment such as the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia storage tanks according to API 500 standards. Electrical equipment must comply with the specifications for these hazardous zones to prevent ignition sources. Ammonia gas may occasionally be released into the atmosphere. To prevent environmental pollution, a flare stack will be installed to combust ammonia released through vents during startup, normal operation, shutdown, or abnormal conditions. The design and layout of the flare stack are determined using FLARESIM simulations and adhere to API 521 to establish escape time based on the generated radiation levels. Safety devices, such as pressure safety valves (PSVs) in key equipment, are designed according to API 521 to mitigate the risk of overpressure hazards. Additionally, temperature, pressure, flow, and level controllers function as protection systems to ensure process stability. Furthermore, fire detection systems compliant with NFPA 72 will be installed in key equipment areas and connected to alarms in the control room to alert workers in case of a fire. With the proposed design, this initiative aims to effectively achieve a zero-accident goal for the ammonia plant. Based on qualitative and quantitative analyses, it can be concluded that ensuring safe operations at PT Enggang Ammonia's plant requires consideration of hazardous areas, particularly key equipment such as the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia storage tanks, classified as Division 2 in accordance with API 500. Electrical equipment must meet specifications for Division 2. The pressure safety valve (PSV) design for the methanator and ammonia storage tanks follows API 521, with orifice designation R for the methanator and T for the ammonia tanks. Two PSVs will be installed for each piece of equipment. Additionally, fire detection systems will be installed for the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia tanks. A protection system comprising an interlock system and process control mechanisms (level, temperature, and pressure) is also essential. Based on FLARESIM simulations and API 521 guidelines, the flare radius is determined to be 128.3 meters with a radiation level of 1.388 kW/m², necessitating the placement of ammonia storage tanks beyond this distance. The flare stack height is set at 80 meters, with a diameter of 28 inches.

Keywords: *Hazardous Area Classification, inherently safer design, flaresim, NFPA 72*

INTRODUCTION

• Background

The continuous development of Indonesia's industrial sector has led to the emergence of new industrial products, raw materials, and job opportunities. To keep pace with this industrial growth, it is essential to enhance the awareness of workers involved in these industries and to develop knowledge regarding occupational safety. If industrial expansion is not accompanied by increased awareness and knowledge of workplace safety, the incidence of occupational accidents, especially in industries involving various hazardous chemicals, is likely to rise.

Workplace accidents are defined as unexpected and unintended incidents that result in loss of life and property (Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 03/Men/1998). According to OHSAS 18001 (1999) as cited by Shariff (2007), workplace accidents are sudden and undesirable events that cause fatalities, injuries, property damage, or time loss. Efforts to minimize workplace accidents are constantly undertaken, as all elements involved—equipment, chemicals, and most importantly, human lives—are invaluable. Unfortunately, workplace accident rates continue to rise. In 2017 alone, 123,000 workplace accident cases were recorded (BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, 2017). The causes of these accidents vary, but according to data from the Workforce Training Bureau, the majority of occupational safety disturbances stem from unsafe behaviors. These include recklessness, failure to follow regulations, non-compliance with standard operating procedures, not using personal protective equipment, and poor physical condition. Only 3% of workplace accidents are attributed to unavoidable causes such as natural disasters, while 24% result from unsafe environments or substandard equipment, and 73% are due to unsafe behaviors.

According to Tarwaka, workplace accidents are generally caused by two main factors: primary causes and underlying causes. Underlying causes in industrial settings include the commitment and participation of management in implementing occupational health and safety (OHS), worker behavior, and workplace conditions, including facilities and the surrounding environment. The primary causes of workplace accidents, on the other hand, include unstandardized implementation of OHS requirements. These primary causes can be categorized as unsafe actions, unsafe conditions, and unsafe man-machine interactions.

In chemical industries, accidents most commonly occur during plant operations. Various hazards may arise from workplace accidents, such as explosions, poisoning, fires, and exposure to hazardous chemicals, all of which pose significant threats to workers and nearby communities. Every company, particularly those in the chemical sector, faces a high risk of accidents. The ammonia industry, which involves highly flammable and explosive chemicals, is one of the most hazardous. One of the most notable ammonia-related workplace accidents occurred at Shanghai Weng's Cold Storage Industrial Co. Ltd in Baoshan, eastern Shanghai, in August 2013, where a liquid ammonia leak from a refrigeration storage unit resulted in the deaths of 15 workers. Additionally, an ammonia tank explosion on March 24, 1992, in Dakar, Senegal, killed 116 people and injured 1,150 others.

These incidents highlight the dangers associated with ammonia industries, which not only threaten workers within the plant but also endanger residents living in surrounding areas. One of the most critical pieces of equipment in an ammonia plant is the ammonia storage tank, which serves to collect the ammonia produced by various processing units. The procedures for ammonia storage vary and are designed to minimize potential risks such as leaks, explosions, and fires. To mitigate these risks, adherence to proper operational standards and the implementation of effective control systems are necessary to prevent accidents, thereby minimizing both property and human losses.

Thus, plant design must incorporate safety measures to ensure compliance with national and international regulations and standards. Implementing an inherently safer design (ISD) is one of the key strategies to ensure plant operations are conducted safely for workers while preventing adverse impacts on surrounding communities.

• Problem Identification

Based on the background discussion, the following issues have been identified for analysis:

1. How should the Hazardous Area Classification be determined for the Methanator, Dryer, and Purifier?

2. What are the appropriate safety and environmental devices, as well as fire detection and protection systems, for the ammonia storage tank area to ensure safe plant operations for workers and prevent adverse effects on the surrounding community?
3. How should the flare stack and ammonia storage tank be designed and positioned in compliance with occupational health and safety (OHS) standards, considering safe distances for workers, residents, and the environment?

- **Objectives and Benefits**

Based on the identified problems, the objectives of this paper are as follows:

1. To determine the hazardous area classification for the methanator, dryer, and purifier to minimize potential hazards for workers and nearby residents.
2. To describe the design of pressure safety valves (PSVs) in accordance with API 521, as well as the fire detection and protection systems for the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia storage tank.
3. To describe the design and layout of the flare stack using FLARESIM simulations to determine the escape time based on the generated radiation levels.

METHODOLOGY

- **Methodology**

In conducting this study, several steps are undertaken to implement inherently safer design (ISD) within the occupational health and safety (OHS) equipment system. These steps are summarized in the problem-solving methodology, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General Methodology of Implementation

1. Determination of Hazard Identification (HAZID) and Hazardous Area Classification

HAZID is a systematic analysis conducted by a critical review team, in which operational and process activities are evaluated to identify potential hazards arising from maloperation or malfunction of equipment and their overall consequences. Hazard identification is a structured and systematic technique for assessing a system and risk management.

To determine hazardous area classification, components in the operational conditions table and fluid composition of the methanator, molecular sieve dryer, and purifier rectifier (Appendix 1) are first identified. This identification is conducted in accordance with the Indian Standard Explosive Atmospheres (IS-IEC-60079-20-1), Part 20, concerning material characteristics for gas and vapor classification. Subsequently, the distance and classification of hazardous areas are determined based on API 500 standards to ensure that the plant operates safely and prevents ignition from electrical equipment. The determination of hazardous zone distances is applied to the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia storage tank.

2. Determination of Safety & Environmental Devices, as well as Fire Detection and Protection Systems, Based on Inherently Safer Design Principles

The determination of safety & environmental devices involves PSV calculations following the recommendations of API Table 4.4, which addresses overpressure protection, blockage, fire case scenarios, and other risks for each equipment unit. The Pressure Safety Valve (PSV) serves as an overpressure protection system. Additionally, fire detection is designed according to NFPA 72 standards in critical equipment areas and is integrated with an alarm system in the control room, ensuring that workers receive immediate alerts in case of fire incidents in specific areas.

3. Determination of Flare Radiation Zones, as well as the Design and Layout of the Flare Stack and Ammonia Storage Tank

In this study, a computational approach is employed using the FLARESIM application to determine the safe radiation zone radius for each equipment unit (methanator, dryer, and purifier). Once the flare safe zone radius values are obtained, the placement pattern of each unit is illustrated using AutoCAD. Furthermore, the methodology for determining the flare safety zone using FLARESIM software is summarized in the following problem-solving approach:

Figure 2. Methodology Workflow Using Flaresim

• Limitations and Assumptions

In this paper, certain limitations are defined to address the determination of the K3 equipment system for the case study, as follows:

1. Scope of Equipment

The study focuses only on the main equipment: methanator, purifier, dryer, and ammonia tank in the ammonia plant.

2. Assumptions:

a. Methanator:

PSV calculation with a methanator feed of 158,713 kg/h

Relative molecular weight of 10.94 kg/kgmol

Operating temperature: 346°C

Operating pressure: 36.7 barg

Set pressure: 40.37 barg

b. Tank:

PSV calculation with a tank capacity of 149,200 kg/h

Relative molecular weight of 17 kg/kgmol

Operating temperature: -33°C

Operating pressure: 1 barg

Set pressure: 1.1 barg

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After establishing the methodology, this chapter will delve deeper into all aspects related to the K3 equipment system based on the principles of inherently safer design to ensure safe plant operations.

The discussion in this chapter broadly covers:

1. Process Description
2. Hazard Identification (HAZID)
3. Recommended K3 Equipment System

• Process Description

The unit under review in this case includes several process equipment, such as the methanator, dryer, and purifier. In the methanator, a methanation process occurs, which aims to convert CO and CO₂ gases, which cannot be absorbed or converted in the HTS, LTS, and CO₂ removal units, into methane using a Ni catalyst. The methanation reaction is exothermic and has the potential to cause excessive heat (overheating) in the reactor.

In the dryer, a drying process takes place using a zeolite catalyst to remove ammonia, residual CO₂, and water from the total synthesis gas stream within a 24-hour drying cycle. In this drying process, it is crucial that no water enters the subsequent process, as water can freeze in the purification unit and cause flow blockages.

The synthesis gas leaving the methanation and drying units will be separated into methane, 50% argon, and approximately 24% nitrogen by liquefying the gas in the purifier. In the purifier, condensation of gas impurities occurs to achieve an H₂/N₂ ratio of 3:1. Under normal conditions, the tank serves as a storage, receiver, and sender of ammonia.

• Hazard Identification (HAZID)

HAZID (Hazard Identification) is a qualitative technique for the initial identification of potential hazards and threats that may affect people, the environment, assets, or reputation. The main benefit of a HAZID study is to provide important input for project development decisions. It is a tool for identifying and explaining HSE hazards and threats at the earliest stages of development or business ventures.

Ammonia exposure may occur due to two possible causes: from programmed activities such as internal inspection programs, and from unplanned incidents or disturbances such as tank system leaks or tank explosions. A schematic for identifying potential conditions that could lead to ammonia release from the tank is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Ammonia Hazard Identification Schematic.

In Table 1., the handling of potential hazards in the ammonia plant is explained.

Table 1. Recommendations for Hazard Handling in the Ammonia Plant

No.	Activities, Source of Exposure/Leak	Recommendation
1	Tank Damage / Leak / Rupture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The ammonia chemical storage tank is designed with a single-wall type. This type is indeed cheaper compared to the double-wall type, but in terms of strength and reliability, it can be considered low. 2. Therefore, it is recommended to implement construction safety features, such as installing additional partitions/enclosures equipped with a foam system unit. In case of a leak, the foam pump should be activated immediately to allow the transfer of ammonia to the urea plant. Additionally, this foam system is also intended to slow down the evaporation rate of ammonia from the leak source. An alternative proposal is to create a partition around the inner walls of the tank.

2	Human Error PSV – Opening Empty Tank	1. From an operational standpoint, operator errors in equipment operation can cause deviations such as overpressure or, conversely, vacuum pressure, leading to tank damage or collapse. Therefore, it is necessary to provide guidelines that operators can always refer to in the form of a pocket-sized operation manual (Standard Operating Procedure) that serves as a reference for operators while working. The manual should include aspects of occupational safety as well as environmental safety.
3	Instrumentation Failure Inaccurate Level Indication	1. Preventive Maintenance should be tightened.
4	Compressor Failure Tank Pressure Increases PSV – Opening	1. Tighten preventive maintenance for the compressor unit. 2. Prepare an emergency diesel generator with an independent transformer.
5	Flange Gasket and Packing Valve Damage / Leak	1. Gasket specifications meet original standards. 2. Correct installation of gaskets/packings. 3. Routine inspections and checks.
6	Hose/Temporary Hose for Ammonia Liquid Transfer Flow Disconnection (during tank emptying program)	1. Properly layout the hose, ensuring good housekeeping in the area. 2. Ensure that hose clamps are securely fastened. 3. Provide protection for hoses crossing roads or pathways.
7	Tank Struck by Lightning	1. Ensure the grounding system functions properly (meeting standard resistance requirements).
8	High Ammonia Waste Concentration in the Chemical Pond (during tank emptying program)	1. Establish rules/regulations. 2. Dilute the remaining ammonia liquid in the tank as much as possible before disposing of it into the chemical pond.
9	Excess Ammonia Liquid Remaining in the Tank (during tank emptying program)	1. Extend the suction line (discharge pump pipe).
10	Emergency Response a. Procedures are not well understood. b. The emergency siren sound is not distinguishable. c. Lack of discipline in using personal protective equipment. d. Insufficient number of "wind direction" indicators.	1. Develop training and socialization programs for employees, contractors, and the community. 2. Prepare sirens with different tones to differentiate emergency response levels. 3. Implement training programs on proper usage, especially for breathing apparatus. 4. Apply sanctions for those who are not disciplined. 5. Increase the installation of wind direction indicators in strategic and visible locations.

• Recommended Safety Equipment System

1. Inherently Safer Design Principle

Inherently safer design refers to the specific design of chemical processes and products to eliminate hazards from manufacturing processes rather than controlling these hazards, thus ensuring safer operations. This principle is applied at all levels of design and operation, from conceptual design to plant design. There are several strategies for applying this principle, including minimizing,

moderating, substituting, and simplifying. In the process, the strategy that may be applied is "moderating." The application of the moderate principle includes determining hazardous area classification, selecting safety and environmental devices, fire detection and protection, and defining safe zone radius for flares.

2. Hazardous Area Classification

When determining hazardous area classification, the properties of the components in the process equipment must first be reviewed. These components include hydrogen, methane, water, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, argon, and nitrogen.

Hydrogen, being a gas, is classified as group IIC based on its Maximum Experimental Safe Gap ($MESG \leq 0.5$ mm) and Minimum Igniting Currents ($MIC < 0.45$), as per IEC 60079-11. Hydrogen's temperature classification is T1, meaning its auto-ignition temperature (AIT) is greater than 450°C , according to IEC 60079. Hydrogen has a relative molecular weight of 2, which is lighter than air (28.82), classifying it as hazardous and belonging to Division 2 based on API 500.

Methane, like natural gas, is classified under group IIA with $MESG < 0.5$ mm or $MIC < 0.45$, according to IEC 60079-11. Its temperature classification is also T1, with an auto-ignition temperature (AIT) greater than 450°C . Methane has a relative molecular weight of 17, which is lighter than air (28.82), classifying it as hazardous and belonging to Division 2 based on API 500.

Water, in this context, refers to hot steam and is classified as a gas. It is classified as group IIC based on $MESG \leq 0.5$ mm and $MIC < 0.45$, according to IEC 60079-11. Its temperature classification is T1, with an AIT greater than 450°C , based on IEC 60079. Water has a relative molecular weight of 18, which is lighter than air (28.82), making it hazardous and classified in Division 2 based on API 500.

On the other hand, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, argon, and nitrogen are not considered flammable materials.

• Safety & Environmental Device and Fire Detection and Protection System

1. Methanator, Dryer, and Purifier

Figure 4. Process Flow Diagram of Methanator, Dryer, and Purifier.

Figure 4. is the process flow diagram for the methanator, dryer, and purifier. The methanator functions to react CO & CO₂ into Methane and Water. The following controls are present in the methanator:

1. The inlet temperature of M-1 (Methanator) is controlled by V-1 A/B.
2. The inlet temperature of K-10 is controlled by the NH₃ flow from E-9.

Some safety aspects related to the methanator are explained as follows:

1. The two control valves, V-1A and V-1B, work in a split range, where V-1A will open to cool the inlet temperature, and conversely, V-1B will open to heat the inlet temperature. V-1A opens fully at 100% and closes at 50%, while V-1B closes at 50% and opens fully at 0%.
2. For protection against HE, the control valve V-1B is set to remain open at a minimum of 5%.
3. V-1A will close and V-1B will open in the event of an air instrument loss or control signal loss. Handjack facilities are provided on both control valves.
4. MOV-6 is an inching valve, controlled through HS-6 with valve position indication ZLO/ZLC-6. MOV is equipped with a handjack and a 1½" bypass line with double BV and bleed for press-up purposes.
5. Both 1½" bypass BVs for press-up must be tightly closed, and the bleed should be fully open after use to prevent the bypass line from containing CO or CO₂ at high concentrations during a shutdown. The valve does not need to be a tight shutoff valve and is used to close the gas flow quickly before MOV-6 closes to isolate the methanator.
6. PV-1 (PIC 1) is a tight shutoff control valve that will close upon air instrument loss or control signal loss. It is also equipped with handjack facilities and isolation BV upstream. To prevent a trip due to thermocouple failure, thermocouples T-1 to T-4 are designed to read very low temperatures in case of damage or burning. A transmitter failure alarm will appear in the DCS.
7. In the event of upset CO or CO₂ levels, an emergency nitrogen line is installed at the methanator outlet. This is to lower the gas temperature entering the shell side of the heat exchanger to prevent overheating (design shell 457°C at a pressure of 40.3 kg/cm²G). If the catalyst bed temperature exceeds design limits, it should be depressurized as soon as possible.
8. Depressurization can be performed by opening the vent line V6-3" at the methanator inlet. For purging and cooling down, nitrogen is introduced from the emergency nitrogen line and vented to the atmosphere via the V6-3" vent line.
9. The pressure at K-10 is monitored and controlled by PIC-5. V-5 will close in the event of air instrument loss or control signal loss. The control valve type is a tight shutoff valve. For overpressure protection, PRV-5 is installed and set to open at 38.3 kg/cm²G, and the downstream line joins the cold vent system.
10. PSV sizing for the methanator is provided in the appendix.

The dryer functions to remove moisture (H₂O) and CO₂ from syngas to below 1 mg/m³v for CO₂ and < 0.1 mg/m³v for H₂O. The following controls are used:

1. Regeneration temperature S-1 A&B is controlled by E-15.
2. The inlet temperature of K-10 is controlled by the NH₃ flow from E-8.

Some safety aspects related to the methanator are explained as follows:

1. If the methanator trips, the program will stop, and MOV inlet and outlet valves (MOV-24 and MOV-25) will close. A common trouble alarm will appear in the DCS as KA-1001, indicating a PLC system problem.
2. The valves at S-1 are designed with the following specifications:
 - All valves are tight shutoff type.
 - All valves are equipped with handjack facilities.
 - All pneumatic control valves will close if there is a loss of air instrument.
 - Isolation valve for S-1A is MOV-24, while for S-1B, it is MOV-25.
3. The catalyst converter is designed with a maximum CO₂ content of 3 mg/m³v in the inlet gas flow.

The purifier functions to condense gas impurities to achieve a H₂/N₂ ratio of 3:1. The following controls are present in the purifier:

1. Regeneration temperature S-1 A&B is controlled by E-15.
2. The inlet temperature of K-10 is controlled by the NH₃ flow from E-8.

Some safety aspects related to the methanator are explained as follows:

1. The purifier can be isolated and bypassed. The bypass line is equipped with double BVs and bleed.
2. Liquid nitrogen has a temperature of -173°C , which can cause serious and rapid injury if it comes into contact with the body. Extra caution must be taken when draining the system. Do not use the drain to normalize the level in case of high-high level conditions. Additionally, nitrogen and argon are heavier than air and will tend to flow downward from the vent line, displacing air at the lowest level and potentially causing suffocation.
3. If the methanator trips, it will activate solenoid AY-27, instructing Valve AV-27 to close in order to maintain the bottom level as long as possible.
4. From time to time, if the system is upset or operating outside normal conditions for a prolonged period, fouling may occur in the HE purifier, such as freezing of water, ammonia, or CO_2 . To evaporate and remove these impurities, the HE is heated and purged with dry gas. This method is called Deriming.
5. Nitrogen that has been heated is required for the deriming procedure.
6. The box is well insulated between the equipment and the box walls, and the insulation must be kept free of water to prevent freezing and heat loss. To ensure this, the box is continuously purged with nitrogen. Nitrogen is supplied from the main header after being let down to the header in the box.

2. Ammonia Tank

In normal conditions, the tank functions as a storage, receiver, and distributor of ammonia. To maintain a pressure of 1 ton in the ammonia liquid, a tank equipped with a refrigeration system (refrigerated storage) is required. The vapor formed in the tank must be continuously compressed and condensed at a certain rate to prevent dangerous pressure increases. This atmospheric pressure is regulated using a PIC (Pressure Indicator Control) and PISLH (Pressure Indicator Switch Low-High) to automatically control the compressor load. If the rate of vapor formation in the tank increases, the compressor load will increase proportionally. Each ammonia storage tank is equipped with 3 compressors that operate automatically. The tank and compressors operate as follows: When the rate of vapor formation in the tank increases, the compressor load will increase proportionally. If the first compressor runs at full load, the second compressor will automatically start. If the rate of vapor formation in the tank decreases, it will cause a reduction in the load, and the refrigeration compressor will stop. If there is heat leakage from outside the tank, reaching the maximum load, the refrigeration compressor or one of the compressors will operate at 25% load. An increase in refrigeration load will cause an automatic increase in compressor load, ensuring that the normal operating pressure inside the tank does not exceed $0.1 \text{ kg/cm}^2\text{G}$. If overpressure occurs in the tank, the product cooling temperature must be checked to ensure it does not exceed 70°C (Design Temperature). The installation of pressure control equipment ensures that any loading errors in the main compressors are detected.

To protect the tank from pressures $\geq 0.15 \text{ kg/cm}^2\text{G}$, the top of the tank is equipped with two safety valves, and one safety valve for each tank is used at 50% capacity, so two safety valves are sufficient for total discharge. During refrigeration, inert gases will automatically be vented to the outside air. In case of an emergency tank, the valve located in the product rundown will close. The tank is designed with a single-wall cylindrical construction.

The ammonia tank construction is equipped with protective insulation to prevent excessive load on the compressor due to ammonia vapor formation. Thermal insulation consists of materials or combinations of materials used to slow the rate of heat transfer due to conduction, convection, and radiation. The purpose of installing insulation is to prevent condensation on surfaces due to operating temperatures below the dew point, prevent the infiltration of air or water vapor from outside the insulation into the insulation, protect surfaces from corrosion, and strengthen the structure. The presence of water in any form—vapor, liquid, or solid—will lower the internal conductivity value as it can cause damage to the insulation or even damage the structure, corrosion, or expansion effects from the water. Water vapor can accumulate in the insulation depending on the hygroscopic properties of the insulation, temperature, ambient conditions, and the effectiveness of the material itself. Nearly all insulation materials are hygroscopic and absorb or lose moisture in proportion to the humidity of the air surrounding them. Therefore, the outer layer of insulation on the ammonia storage tank is covered with a tight, non-hygroscopic plate material.

The instrumentation system is the control and safety system for the tank's operation, which includes safety and control devices for tank pressure, high-pressure control valves, compressor load controllers (75-100%, 50-75%, 25-50%), load reduction (100-75%, 75-50%, 50-25%), low-pressure alarms, automatic compressor trip, and low-pressure protection (vacuum breaker).

The level safety system consists of various alarms, such as LSHH (Level Switch High High), which will close the inlet valve, LSH (Level Switch High) for high-level alarm, LSL (Level Switch Low) for low-level alarm, and LSL (Level Switch Low-Low) for low-low-level alarm. The outlet valve will close, and the loading pump will stop. The instrumentation system on the tank must be reliable and function as intended. However, it is recommended that the tank's inlet "block valve," which controls the flow of ammonia from the synloop plant, is still a manual "block valve." If a "High Level" condition occurs in the tank, the operator may take a long time to complete the valve closure task. In the event of an ammonia leak in the area, this will make the process even more challenging. Therefore, the manual "block valve" should be replaced with a "Quick Valve" type that operates interlocked with the instrumentation system. A preventive maintenance program, which occasionally requires bypassing the interlock, must have standardized guidelines regarding time and responsibility levels. Additionally, the Restroke-Control Valve program often does not include improvements to the position indication of the open/close valve, causing discrepancies in how operators report the position. PSV sizing for the ammonia tank is displayed in the Appendix.

3. Preparation of Facilities and Equipment to Handle Ammonia Leaks

Uncontrolled ammonia leaks from the tank system, whether from planned or unplanned activities, can lead to industrial accidents. To anticipate this, emergency response procedures have been established, including all necessary facilities and periodic training programs. Several facilities have been prepared, including:

1. Assembly Point The assembly point is intended as a gathering place to facilitate the evacuation process. Coordination and transportation become easier with the presence of the assembly point, which is selected based on:
 1. Strategic location
 2. Sufficient capacity
 3. Ease of vehicle access
 4. The safest location

2. Temporary Safe Building (GAS)

The Temporary Safe Building is a work facility that, in an emergency situation, is used for temporary medical assistance before victims are transferred to a hospital. In normal conditions, the Temporary Safe Building is equipped with basic medical facilities, including oxygen bottles for breathing assistance, which are always in standby mode, a set of stretchers, and First Aid (P3K) equipment.

3. Emergency Response Command Post

The command post serves as the coordination center for emergency response. The command post building must meet the following criteria:

1. Equipped with safety measures and gas management capabilities
2. Easily accessible
3. Equipped with communication and transportation facilities
4. Ideally positioned at a high location, allowing the commander/officers to see in all directions
5. Equipped with adequate personal protective equipment

4. Wind Direction Indicator

A wind direction indicator is installed at strategic locations, typically high and visible, to indicate the wind direction. Understanding wind direction is crucial for determining the safest escape route from ammonia danger.

Figure 5. Wind Direction Principle for Evacuation

5. Breathing Apparatus (BA) Protective Equipment

The Breathing Apparatus (BA) is a critical safety equipment designed to protect workers from the dangers of ammonia gas. The apparatus consists of a compressed air cylinder, typically containing pure air at a pressure of 150-200 bar. The working principle of the BA is that the air pressure is gradually reduced to match the normal atmospheric pressure. Exhaled air is expelled through an exhaust valve, ensuring that the user remains safe in an environment filled with ammonia gas. Currently, the company has a limited supply of 169 BA units, which is insufficient considering the number of employees at the plant. As a result, these units are only placed in high-risk areas. Given the potential for ammonia leaks, it is highly recommended that the company increase the number of Breathing Apparatus. Ideally, each operator should have one unit per shift for better preparedness and safety.

6. Gas-tight Room (Ruang Kedap Gas)

In case of an emergency, it is essential to have personnel in the control room (Ruang Kedap Gas) to ensure the safety of the plant until operations can return to normal. The control room serves as a safe area for staff to remain in while managing the plant's shutdown, thus preventing additional risks from an abnormal shutdown process. Moreover, the staff inside the control room are responsible for activating emergency equipment and taking necessary corrective actions. The Ruang Kedap Gas should meet the following conditions:

- Air-tight: No contaminants or harmful air can enter the room.
- Adequate Oxygen Supply: The room must have sufficient oxygen levels, supported by a make-up oxygen system to ensure a constant flow of breathable air.
- Safe Working Environment: Personnel should be able to perform their duties safely within the room, and oxygen needs should be calculated based on the number of people inside, the room's volume, and the activities taking place. This ensures that staff are protected from "oxygen deficiency" and other potential hazards.

7. Fire Hydrant System

The Fire Hydrant system is a permanent facility designed to address fire hazards in the plant, especially given the presence of flammable and explosive materials such as natural gas and ammonia. Fire hydrants play a crucial role not only in fire suppression but also in managing chemical spills, particularly ammonia leaks. Ammonia and Water: Since ammonia dissolves in water, spraying the leak with water from the fire hydrants helps reduce ammonia's concentration in the air and limits its spread.

Hydrant Water Supply: The water supply for the hydrants is stored in a tank with a specified capacity and is equipped with pumps for water transfer. The pump system is designed to maintain a pressure of 6-6.5 kg/cm² across all hydrants, ensuring adequate water flow. The system includes:

- 2 Diesel Pumps (reciprocating) and
- 2 Electric Motor Pumps (centrifugal).

The number of pumps is adjusted according to the water usage needs, to maintain the hydrant pressure at a constant 6 kg/cm².

8. Piping System

The piping system should use an ammonia inlet valve (for feeding) that is not manually operated, such as a Quick Valve, because generally ammonia plants still use Block Valves, which can be dangerous if located far from the operator's control. This could lead to a delay in reaching the valve in case of emergency.

9. Lightning Protection, Grounding, and Bonding System

The tank system needs to be equipped with a lightning rod to protect the tank from potential lightning strikes. Similarly, electrical equipment such as pump motors and their panels must be fitted with a grounding system to safely dissipate electrical faults. To prevent electrostatic hazards, especially during ammonia loading activities onto ships, the Loading Arm system must be equipped with bonding tools. Grounding system checks are typically done during the annual Turnaround (a comprehensive inspection and maintenance process). It is recommended that these inspections be conducted semi-annually, based on previous results that show fluctuations in resistance readings.

10. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Personal protective equipment must be carefully considered, especially with regard to workers' awareness of the importance of using PPE, as it is critical to protect them from workplace accidents and to ensure preparedness for emergency response situations.

11. Fire Detection

- Fire Water System

The automatic sprinkler system is a fire suppression device that disperses water through nozzles, which have deflector shields that allow the water to spray evenly in all directions.

- Fire Detector System

The fire detector system is an integrated system designed to detect signs of fire and provide early warnings for evacuation. The system is followed by automatic or manual action through a firefighting system. Fire alarms provide unrivaled accuracy and ease of use for protecting multi-story buildings, installers, and firefighting personnel.

A fire detector is a device that receives input and operates automatically. There are four types of fire detectors:

- Heat Detector
- Smoke Detector
- Flame Detector
- Gas Detector

The main components of the fire alarm system include:

1. MCFA (Main Control Fire Alarm)

MCFA is the main equipment in the protection system. Its function is to receive input signals from detectors and other protection components (e.g., fixed heat detectors, smoke detectors, ROR heat detectors, etc.).

2. Detectors

A detector is a device that functions as an automatic input receiver. There are four types of fire detectors:

- Heat Detector

A Heat Detector detects changes in thermal energy (heat) caused by fire. There are two types of heat detectors: one with a fixed temperature limit and the other detecting sudden temperature increases.

- Flame Detector
A Flame Detector detects the presence of flames. There are three types: optical sensors, ionization sensors, and thermocouples.
- Smoke Detector
A Smoke Detector provides protection, especially in large or multi-story buildings, and is essential for spaces with differing environmental conditions. For example, a heat detector can be used in hot areas with a set threshold to detect any temperature changes. Smoke and heat detectors work together to detect anomalies that could indicate a fire.
- Gas Detector (Fire Gas Detector)
Gas leaks are one of the leading causes of major industrial accidents, due to the hazardous nature of certain gases. Early warning systems and gas detectors are vital to prevent fatalities and damage.

Common gases that are measured include:

1. Hydrocarbons
2. Carbon monoxide (CO)
3. Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
4. Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S)
5. Oxygen (O₂)

Types of Gas Detectors:

1. Combustible/Flammable Gas Detector (Rexplosimeter)
2. Toxic Gas Detector
3. Oxygen Analyzer
4. Combination Gas Detector

For flammable gas detection:

1. Flash Point: The minimum temperature at which a liquid forms a mixture that can ignite. When exposed to a flame, it will briefly catch fire.
2. Auto Ignition Temperature: The minimum temperature at which a substance can ignite without a spark or flame.
- 3.

Flammability Range:

1. Explosive Limit (Flammability Range): The concentration of vapors in the air that can cause a fire when exposed to a spark or flame.
2. Lower Explosive Limit (LEL): The minimum concentration of vapor in the air required for a fire to occur.
3. Upper Explosive Limit (UEL): The maximum concentration of vapor in the air that can burn. Beyond this concentration, the fire will extinguish.

- **Safe Radius Zone for Flare**

The combustion process is carried out in a flare stack, which is a vertical burning device designed to protect process equipment from overpressure. This installation serves as a safety system to reduce pressure within the equipment. In addition to providing safety, flaring gas aims to minimize environmental pollution, as releasing gas into the atmosphere without prior combustion would have a negative impact on the surrounding environment (Gervet, 2007).

In this plant, to prevent environmental pollution caused by the release of ammonia gas into the atmosphere, a flare stack will be installed. The flare stack functions to burn ammonia that is released through the vent during start-up, normal shut-down, or other abnormal conditions. The results of the Flaresim simulation can be found in the appendix.

CONCLUSION

In an effort to ensure the safe operation of the ammonia plant at PT. Enggang Ammonia for both workers and the surrounding environment, the following considerations must be taken into account:

1. Hazardous Areas: Particularly around main equipment such as the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia tanks, these areas are classified as Division 2 in accordance with API 500. Electrical equipment must meet the specifications for Division 2.
2. Pressure Safety Valve (PSV) Design: The PSV design for the methanator and ammonia tanks follows API 521, with an orifice designation of R for the methanator and T for the ammonia tanks. Two PSVs are installed on each piece of equipment. Additionally, fire detection systems are required for the methanator, dryer, purifier, and ammonia tanks. A protection system, including an interlock system and process control (level, temperature, and pressure), is also necessary.
3. Flare System: Based on the Flaresim simulation and API 521 guidelines, the flare radius is determined to be 128.3 meters with a radiation level of 1.388 kW/m². Therefore, the ammonia tank must be placed at a distance greater than 128.3 meters. The flare stack height is set at 80 meters with a diameter of 28 inches.

RECOMMENDATION

1. It is recommended to install a minimum of two PSVs on each piece of equipment/vessel.
2. To prevent the risk of vacuum in the ammonia tank, it is advised to install a vacuum breaker on the tank.

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